

OLIVIA HOLMES
*ASSEMBLING THE LYRIC SELF: AUTHORSHIP FROM TROUBADOUR
SONG TO ITALIAN POETRY BOOK*
Minneapolis-London: University of Minnesota Press, 2000. ix, 222 pp.

Two of the long held tenets in Mediaeval Studies are that Petrarch represents the emergence of the individual and literary self-consciousness. In this far-reaching study, Olivia Holmes demonstrates how convictions such as these have long hidden the actual development of the author-ordered book of poetry and ideas of authorship. By returning to the original manuscripts that circulated in and influenced the Middle Ages, Holmes analyses lyric works in their original context, as contemporaries would have read them, disregarding modern editions, which are often unfaithful to the works' true arrangement. She examines the emergence of historical self-hood and the modern figure of the author in lyric cycles of the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries. The "discovery of the individual" and Burckhardtian ideas of medieval conformism and Renaissance individualism lie outside the scope of her argument, her intention is rather, to illustrate the emergence of an "implied author" in early Provençal and Italian lyric manuscripts.

Holmes divides her book into nine chapters. The first chapter provides an overview of her argument, the historical atmosphere, and conclusions and contributions of other studies. The second and third discuss the lyric production of Uc de Saint Circ and Guittone d'Arezzo respectively. The fourth looks at the importance of the relatively minor cycles of Rustico Filippi, Monte Andrea and "La corona di casistica amorosa", as found inserted inside a larger anthology. The final four chapters examine Guiraut Riquier, Dante's *Vita Nova*, Nicolò de' Rossi and Petrarch's *Canzoniere*.

Holmes frames her discussion with the increase of vernacular literacy in Western Europe in the thirteenth century and the corresponding appearance of a large body of secular literature for the general public, and the emergence of the single-author book of poems, finding its model in Petrarch's *Canzoniere*. The first manuscripts were multiauthor anthologies of troubadour lyric compiled by scribes, written in Old Occitan around the middle of the thirteenth century. These first manuscripts were the simple transposition of what was predominantly an oral tradition and represent a backward-looking attempt at preservation. The next step in historical systemization was the insertion of introductory *vidas* and *razos* in many of these anthologies. Holmes notes that within fifty years of these first compilations, single-author collections organized by the poet himself, in such a way as to represent the poet's experience through time, i.e. a book of poetry, also appeared. In these three events, in the transition from oral to

written, individual poems and whole *corpora* took on fixed forms, vernacular poets developed a more acute desire to claim their work and give it definitive form, and, oral lyric poetry, which can have a sense of being situated in an eternal present, in the written form, gained a sense of historical time when placed in relation to other texts. Later author-ordered texts were no longer transcriptions of an oral experience, but events in themselves that create an internal sense of time.

In the case of Italian vernacular lyric, it seems to be part of a written tradition that was divorced from music from the beginning (p. 12). The predominance of the written caused a division of poetry and music that broke the sense of circularity created by music and the mutability of orally performed poetry. The varying stanza orderings in early troubadour manuscripts suggest that the stanzas may not have had a fixed order. However, Holmes argues, it is characteristic of a written text to fix order and represent the passage of time more effectively than oral performance. Holmes sees the divide, caused by writing, of words and music, as leading almost inevitably from the ordering of stanzas within a *canzone*, to the ordering of poems in a *canzoniere*.

The modifications of the Occitan *tenso* are an important step in this development. In its original form, it was a debate poem in which different troubadours contributed alternating stanzas. Transplanted in Italy, as the *tenzone*, poets exchanged whole sonnets, creating a cycle, leading to the feigned *tenzone*, composed by only one poet that relays a story between lover and lady. An important precedent of this sort of *tenso* was composed in Italy by the troubadour Raimbaut de Vaqueiras, and Italian examples are discussed by Holmes in the work of Guittone d'Arezzo and Rustico Filippi.

Holmes also reveals the influential role played by the practices of scribes and notaries in the compilation of materials. Scribal methods of organizing anthologies thematically or narratively served as the models for the books poets would later construct themselves. Notaries, by definition, compile autograph documents into personal registers and their participation, such as that of Giacomo da Lentini, in the earliest phases of Italian poetry is well known. It is therefore not surprising if later poets looking at early poetic collections did not learn something from their organization, or if Petrarch, son to a line of notaries, was influenced by their practices.

Beginning with the 12 *canso* cycle of Uc de Saint Circ, found in the oldest extant Provençal codex, Holmes reveals how the *cansos* combine to tell a unified story. Located under the heading of the poet's name, the *cansos* are told in the first person, they are connected by formal and lexical unifiers, and among them is a "chanson de change", which lends a sense of closure, and therefore of elapsed time, to the cycle. The organization of this cycle creates a story that the reader would identify with Uc's life. Holmes argues that, at

this stage in history, Uc's songs probably originate in the written form, that writing allowed him to see all his work as part of a macrotext, and thus give it a sense of chronology. What Holmes finds most important is that in fact, the 12 *canso* cycle forms a narrative identified with a historical personage, to be found in the earliest extant troubadour book.

Holmes traces the expansion of these characteristics through all of the cycles considered in her study. All of these cycles create an internal sense of time that seems to tell a story related to the author's life. The "chanson de change", or, conversion song, is one of the ways the effect of progression is given. Uc changes from one lady to another and reflects on how he was before the change, lexically connecting previous songs that describe who he is now. Guittone converts: in his cycle, too complex not to have been author ordered, he begins as Fra Guittone and recants his previous poetry, which follows his conversion poetry in the manuscript, and lends a sense of spiritual improvement to the work. Holmes suggests that the credibility of the conversion may be related to the ultimate historical success of the narrative. Indeed, Guittone radically recants his prior production, however such drastic changes are not always considered so believable. On the other hand, in the *Vita Nova*, Dante's conversion and belief in all that he makes of Beatrice is most sincere; and then we have Petrarch, who never converts, but convinced centuries of readers of how much he desired to. Time is portrayed also with the anniversary poem, used by Dante, Nicolò de Rossi and Petrarch, while Guiraut Riquier numbered and dated his poems. Thus, by means of a number of techniques a narrative identifiable with the author and his life develops.

By returning to original manuscripts, Holmes illustrates how an author or compiler consciously implied a sense of history or completion with the simple insertion of a cycle within a larger volume. Holmes notes that the manner in which Guittone's corpus is placed in relation to that of the other poets in the codex gives the reader a sense of arriving at the summit of Italian literature. In Guittone's case, it is not obvious if this was the author's intention, but in Dante's, we know that it was. The scribal placement of the *Vita Nova*, with its opening words, "*incipit vita nova*", near the beginning of the manuscript Holmes exemplifies, but after poems by Guinizelli and Cavalcanti, would definitely create in the reader the expectation of a break from what preceded it. Therefore, the very organization of the codices also gave the reader an idea of lyric history.

In going back to the manuscripts, and analyzing them as integral units, Holmes eloquently reveals the seeds of the modern vernacular book of poetry, showing how the different authors discussed were conscious of each other and the impact they had. Tracing the emergence of vernacular lyric narrative from the earliest extant manuscript, Holmes proves with overwhelming evidence that Petrarch may have produced the archetype of the

lyric book of poetry, but he certainly was not without precedents to draw from. The long held tenets regarding Petrarch are, as Holmes states, more correctly associated with “his ability to convince posterity of his sincerity” (p. 182). However, reverence for Petrarch’s achievement should no longer veil the true development of the lyric self. Holmes’ groundbreaking study demands a re-reading of texts as they were transmitted, in order for their real impact to be measured and the development of lyric authorship in the vernacular tradition to be truly understood. This extensively researched work will be of great interest to scholars and of fundamental importance to students of Italian mediaeval literature.

BRYAN LEFERMAN

University of Windsor,
Windsor, Ontario